

A prospective study on accuracy of methylene blue dye guided low axillary sampling in staging of axilla in breast cancer

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15741578>

Article Received: 15-May-2025, Revised: 05-June-2025, Accepted: 25-June-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Breast cancer management has transitioned from radical surgeries to breast-conserving and oncoplastic techniques. Axillary staging has similarly evolved from axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) to sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) to minimize morbidity. However, radiotracer-based SLNB is costly and often unavailable in low-resource settings. Methylene blue dye (MBD)-guided low axillary sampling (LAS) may offer a cost-effective alternative for accurate axillary staging in such contexts. **Aim:** To evaluate the diagnostic accuracy of MBD-guided LAS for axillary staging in early-stage breast cancer with clinically node-negative axillae. **Methodology:** This prospective study enrolled 25 biopsy-proven breast cancer patients with clinically node-negative axillae at Department of Surgery, University college of Medical Sciences (UCMS) and Guru Teg Bahadur Hospital (GTBH) from May 2023 to November 2024. Inclusion criteria included T1–T2 tumors with no prior axillary surgery. After periareolar injection of 5 ml MBD and massage, patients underwent tumor excision, MBD-guided LAS and ALND. Lymph nodes from axillary levels I–III were histopathologically analyzed. Diagnostic performance metrics, including sensitivity, specificity, false-negative rate (FNR), and accuracy, were calculated using descriptive statistics. **Results:** The mean patient age was 47.9 ± 13.1 years, with most tumors classified as T2 invasive ductal carcinoma. MBD identified sentinel nodes in 18 of 25 patients (84% detection rate). LAS correctly identified nodal metastases in 15 of 16 node-positive cases (93.8%), yielding a sensitivity of 94.1%, specificity of 100%, FNR of 6.3%, and diagnostic accuracy of 96.2%. No adverse reactions to MBD were reported. **Conclusion:** MBD-guided LAS is a safe, cost-effective, and accurate method for axillary staging in early-stage breast cancer in resource-limited settings. Its high sensitivity, specificity, and low FNR support its use as a viable alternative to radiotracer-based SLNB, enhancing access to precise staging where advanced technologies are unavailable.

Keywords: Axillary staging, Breast cancer, Methylene blue dye, Low axillary sampling, Sentinel lymph node biopsy, Diagnostic accuracy

INTRODUCTION:

Breast cancer is the most frequently diagnosed malignancy among women globally, accounting for 13.5% of all cancer cases in India as per GLOBOCAN 2020 estimates [1]. By 2030, nearly 2 million new cases are projected annually worldwide, with India anticipating over 216,000 cases by 2025, representing 28.2% of female cancers [2,3]. In India, the age-standardized incidence rate rose by 39.1% from 1990 to 2016, with urban areas and northeastern states reporting higher rates [4,5]. Despite advances, late-stage diagnosis remains a critical challenge, driven by limited awareness, complex referral pathways, inadequate diagnostic infrastructure, and high out-of-pocket costs [6]. Socioeconomic and cultural barriers further exacerbate delays, contributing to suboptimal

survival rates, with a 5-year survival rate of 66.1% compared to 84% globally [7,8].

Breast cancer management has evolved from radical surgeries, such as modified radical mastectomy and axillary lymph node dissection (ALND), to breast-conserving and oncoplastic approaches [9]. Axillary staging has similarly progressed, with sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) replacing ALND for early-stage, clinically node-negative patients to reduce complications like lymphedema and impaired shoulder mobility [10,11]. However, SLNB using dual-tracer methods (radioisotopes and vital dyes) is resource-intensive, requiring nuclear medicine facilities and posing radiation safety concerns [12]. In low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) like India, these

logistical and financial barriers limit access to standard SLNB [13].

Methylene blue dye (MBD) offers a cost-effective alternative for SLNB, with advantages including ease of use, minimal adverse effects, and no radiation exposure [14,15]. Despite its rapid diffusion and potential for tissue staining, MBD achieves sentinel node detection rates of 70–85% [16]. In settings lacking nuclear medicine infrastructure, low axillary sampling (LAS), involving targeted lymph node removal from the lower axilla, has emerged as a practical staging method with false-negative rates comparable to SLNB [17,18]. Combining MBD with LAS may enhance node identification and staging accuracy. This study evaluates the feasibility, accuracy, and clinical utility of MBD-guided LAS for axillary staging in early-stage breast cancer patients with clinically node-negative axillae.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study Design and Ethical Considerations

This prospective observational study was conducted at a tertiary care center following approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC approval number: [IECHR-2023-59-78]). The sample size was calculated based on a reported sensitivity of 89.5% and specificity of 96.6% for methylene blue dye (MBD)-guided sentinel lymph node biopsy, as per Omranipour et al. [1]. Assuming 20% precision, 90% power, and a 5% significance level, a minimum sample size of 36 patients was required. Due to limited availability of eligible cases within the study period (January 2023 to March 2024), 25 patients were enrolled.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS:

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Participants retained the right to withdraw at any time without any compromise to their clinical care. Data security and patient privacy were upheld throughout the study.

Patient Selection:

Female patients of any age with biopsy-proven breast cancer and clinically node-negative axillae (cN0) were included. Exclusion criteria comprised locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer, male breast cancer, node-negative status post-neoadjuvant chemotherapy, or unwillingness to provide informed consent. All participants provided written informed consent after being informed of the study's purpose, procedures, risks, and benefits. Patient confidentiality was strictly maintained in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Methylene Blue Dye Preparation and Administration:

A 1% MBD solution was prepared by dissolving 1 g of methylene blue in 100 ml of sterile distilled water. Under general anesthesia, 5 ml of the solution was injected periareolarly into the subdermal plane in affected breast, followed by a 5-minute gentle massage to facilitate lymphatic migration of the dye.

Surgical Procedure:

Low axillary sampling (LAS) was performed prior to definitive breast surgery, which consisted of either wide local excision or modified radical mastectomy. The axilla was accessed via an incision near the second and third digitations of the serratus anterior muscle. The LAS boundaries were defined superiorly by the intercostobrachial nerve and inferiorly by the angular vein. All blue-stained lymph nodes, palpable or enlarged nodes, and nodes connected to blue lymphatic channels were excised during LAS.

Subsequently, axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) was performed up to Level II in all patients. Dissection was extended to Level III if intraoperative findings indicated Level II nodal involvement. Interpectoral (Rotter's) nodes were excised in all cases. Lymph nodes from each anatomical level (Lower Level I, Upper Level I, Level II, and Level III, if applicable) were collected in separate containers and submitted for histopathological analysis.

Histopathological Analysis:

Histopathological examination using hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) staining served as the gold standard for detecting nodal metastases. Both micrometastases and macrometastases were recorded. The primary outcome measures were the sensitivity and false-negative rate (FNR) of MBD-guided LAS in detecting nodal metastases. Secondary outcomes included the mean number of lymph nodes retrieved per anatomical level.

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics summarized demographic and clinical characteristics. Continuous variables were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) or based on data distribution. Categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Diagnostic performance metrics, including sensitivity, specificity, FNR, and diagnostic accuracy, were calculated by comparing LAS results with ALND histopathological findings. Statistical analyses were performed using [software name, e.g., SPSS version 26] with a significance level of $p < 0.05$.

Preoperative marking of peritumoral region

Figure 1: Injection of methylene blue dye in the periareolar area

Figure 2A

Figure 2B

Figure 2A: Methylene blue stained lymph node; Figure 2B: Blue stained and unstained lymph nodes extracted from low axillary dissection sample

RESULTS:

Demographic characteristics of the study population:

Most patients (40.0%) were aged between 41-50 years, followed by 6 (24.0%) patients in the 31-40-year age group. Mean age of study population was 47.92 years with a standard deviation of 13.06 years. Age distribution of the study population is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Age distribution of study population

Age group (year)	Number of patients (n=25)	Percentage(%)
20 -30	1	4.0
31-40	6	24.0
41-50	10	40.0
51-60	4	16.0
61-70	2	8.0
71-80	2	8.0%
Mean±SD	47.92±13.06	

The largest group comprising of 9 patients (36.0%), belonged to the lower middle socioeconomic class. This was followed by 8 patients (32.0%) in the upper lower class and 7 patients (28.0%) in the upper middle class. (According to modified Kuppuswamy scale, 2024)

Majority of 14 (56.0%) patients had no reported chronic illnesses. Among those with comorbidities, 4 patients (16.0%) had hypothyroidism. Two patients (8.0%) each had history of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), and hypertension along with hypothyroidism, and cerebrovascular accident (CVA). Additionally, one patient (4.0%) had history of pulmonary Koch's disease.

Clinical characteristics of the study population:

Majority of patients (72.0%) had lumps located in upper outer quadrant. The upper inner quadrant and upper outer quadrant involving the retro areolar region each accounted for 2 patients (8.0%). Only 1 patient (4.0%) had a lump located in lower outer quadrant. Majority of 16 patients (64.0%) presenting with lumps were classified as T2-sized lumps, followed by 9 patients (36.0%) with T1-sized lumps while there were no cases (0.0%) with T3-sized lumps.

On imaging investigations, the largest group, consisting of 10 patients (40.0%), had findings classified as BIRADS IV, followed by 7 patients (28.0%) with BIRADS V results, 5 patients (20.0%) had indeterminate findings classified as BIRADS 0, while 2 patients (8.0%) were in the BIRADS VI category. Only 1 patient (4.0%) was classified as BIRADS III.

Surgical procedures:

In this study, types of surgery performed on the 25 patients was predominantly breast conserving surgery (BCS), with 19 patients (76.0%) undergoing this procedure. The remaining 6 patients (24.0%) underwent modified radical mastectomy (MRM). Majority of patients, 21 (84.0%), underwent axillary dissection involving levels I and II of the axillae. A smaller group, 4 patients (16.0%), had axillary dissection that included levels I, II, and III group of nodes.

The axillary dissection specimens with a mean of 6.6 (range: 4–9) at low-level I, 8.2 n (range: 5–12) at upper-level I, 5 (range: 4–7) at level II, and 2.7 (range: 2–4) at level III when dissection was performed. Number of nodes at different levels of axillary dissection specimen shown at table 2.

Table 2: Number of nodes at different levels of axillary dissection specimen

Axillary level	Mean	Range
Low level I	6.6	4-9
Upper level I	8.2	5-12
Level II	5	4-7
Level III (when done)	2.7	2-4

In the axillary dissection specimens (n=25), 64% (16 cases) showed positive axillae, while 36% (9 cases) showed negative axillae after histopathological examination. Out of 25 patients, sentinel nodes using methylene blue technique could be identified in 21 (84%) patients while in 4 (%) patients MBD dye did

not stain any nodes. Hence the **identification rate using MBD** in our study was **84%** only. Out of 16 patients with metastasis in axilla, LAS sample positive in 93.75 % patients whereas LAS negative in 6.25% patients. Status of LAS in positive axillae shown on table 3.

Table 3: Status of LAS in positive axillae

	Frequency (n=16)	Percentage (%)
LAS positive	15	93.75
LAS negative	1	6.25

Diagnostic Accuracy of MBD guided LAS:

Out of 16 positive axillae after axillary dissection, on 15 patients low axillary sample was positive whereas in one patient LAS sample was negative. **Sensitivity** of methylene blue guided low axillary sampling was 94.1% whereas **specificity** came out to be 100%. **False negative rate (FNR)** of the study was 6.25% and **accuracy** of methylene blue guided low axillary sampling in detection of axillary metastasis was 96.15%. (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Identification rate, sensitivity, specificity, false negative rate and accuracy of MBD guided LAS

DISCUSSION:

The surgical management of axillary lymph nodes in breast cancer has evolved significantly over the past few decades. Initially, extensive dissections involving level III axillary lymph node dissection (ALND) were the norm. However, with advancements in breast cancer staging and a better understanding of tumor biology, there has been a marked shift towards de-escalation of axillary surgery. Techniques such as sentinel lymph node biopsy (SLNB) have become the standard in early-stage breast cancer with clinically negative axilla [15–17]. In highly selected patients, axillary surgery may even be omitted [30]. Despite these advances, resource-constrained settings often lack the facilities necessary for SLNB, particularly radioisotope-based methods [18,19]. Consequently, many patients still undergo ALND even when the axilla is clinically negative, leading to overtreatment and associated morbidity [14].

To bridge this gap, alternatives such as four-node sampling and MBD-guided SLNB have been adopted in several low-resource centers with promising results [20,27]. Low axillary sampling (LAS), involving removal of nodes from the inferior half of level I axilla, is a simple and inexpensive technique. This study was designed to assess whether combining LAS with methylene blue dye (MBD) localization could improve nodal staging accuracy and reduce false-negative rates [28,29].

The mean age of the study population was 47.9 ± 13.06 years, with the highest proportion between 41 and 50 years, which is consistent with the demographic pattern observed in other Indian studies [3,4]. A majority of patients belonged to the lower middle and upper lower socioeconomic strata, emphasizing the importance of exploring cost-effective diagnostic options in such populations. The most common comorbidity was hypothyroidism, followed by diabetes

and hypertension. In terms of tumor characteristics, the upper outer quadrant was the most frequently involved site (72%), followed by central and other quadrants, which aligns with global trends [6,7]. Most patients presented with T2 tumors (64%), followed by T1 (36%), indicating early-stage disease suitable for breast-conserving surgery and SLNB [15–17]. BIRADS IV and V were the most common imaging categories, further supporting early diagnosis.

Pathologically, invasive ductal carcinoma was the predominant subtype (88%), which is consistent with literature [13,14]. A smaller proportion had ductal carcinoma in situ (8%) and invasive lobular carcinoma (4%). Similar distributions have been reported in large breast cancer cohorts [5,6]. All patients underwent axillary clearance to evaluate the accuracy of the technique. Of these, 84% underwent level I and II dissection, while 16% had level III dissection as well. The mean number of nodes retrieved was consistent with accepted standards for adequate axillary staging [28,30]. Notably, blue-stained nodes were identified in 84% of patients using methylene blue dye. While this identification rate is somewhat lower than that achieved with dual-tracer methods (which often exceed 90%), it is consistent with previously reported ranges for MBD alone (70–80%) [20,26].

The diagnostic performance of MBD-guided LAS was encouraging. Sensitivity was 93.75%, specificity was 100%, false-negative rate (FNR) was 6.25%, and overall diagnostic accuracy was 96.15%. These results are in line with or better than many published reports. Vadodariya et al. reported 90.47% sensitivity and 93% accuracy using MBD, while Somshekhar et al. reported a sensitivity of 96.2% using a dual-tracer method [21,22]. The relatively low FNR in our study indicates that combining LAS with MBD may enhance detection of nodal metastases in a reliable manner. Though, radioisotope and ICG-based techniques offer higher detection rates, they require logistical support and equipment that are often unavailable in public-sector hospitals or smaller centers in India [18,19]. Our findings suggest that MBD-guided LAS can offer a practical alternative in such settings, without compromising much on diagnostic accuracy. Importantly, this method retains the benefits of being low-cost, safe, and technically straightforward [20–22].

Studies such as those by Patil et al. and Özdemir et al. have shown comparable sensitivity and accuracy with MBD alone, supporting its role in selective axillary staging [21,22]. Moreover, innovations such as the use of carbon nanoparticles or hybrid tracers have shown potential for further improving sentinel node detection in the future, but these are still largely unavailable in resource-limited environments [29,30].

In summary, this study demonstrates that methylene blue dye-guided low axillary sampling is a safe,

feasible, and reasonably accurate method for axillary staging in early breast cancer. It offers a cost-effective alternative to standard SLNB, especially in settings where dual-tracer methods are not viable. Further large-scale, multicentric studies are warranted to validate these findings and to optimize training protocols for wider adoption.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

The present study has certain limitations. The most significant limitation is the small sample size, which may restrict the generalizability of the findings. Although the average number of lymph nodes retrieved through methylene blue dye (MBD)-guided low axillary sampling [mean 6.6, range 4–9] was higher than that reported in several other studies, this did not translate into a lower false-negative rate. Additionally, the identification rate of sentinel lymph nodes in this study was lower compared to most published reports using MBD. This discrepancy could be attributed to the small sample size and the inherent variability of nodal sampling techniques.

CONCLUSION:

Methylene blue-guided low axillary sampling (LAS) demonstrated high sensitivity (93.75%) and diagnostic accuracy (96.15%), indicating effective detection of axillary nodal involvement and improved lymph node yield. The false-negative rate was low (6.25%), aligning with findings from other studies and confirming its reliability as a staging tool. Given that methylene blue is a low-cost and widely available tracer, it serves as a practical alternative to radiocolloids, particularly in resource-limited healthcare settings. The technique was also safe and well-tolerated, with no adverse reactions reported in any of the patients included in the study.

Conflict of Interest; None

Funding: Nil

Source of Support: Nil

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